

POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE MEANINGS OF COLOR ADJECTIVES

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One of the main human senses is a vision of the world in colour. Each person receives a lot of information through the work of the senses. It is wellknown that the work of the organs of visual perception is universal for each person and it doesn't matter what language he or she speaks.

Each language has its own colour scheme which reflects the features of mentality, history of the people, culture and the world of view. Colour has a complex range of symbolic meanings that reveal the inner world of people of different culture. Moral and aesthetic categories, estimates of human activity are expressed with the help of colour.

Color psychology is the study of how colors affect people's behavior, mental state, or physiological processes. Colors influence our purchases, our emotions, and even our memories. Ideas related to the psychology of color are widely used in the fields of marketing and design. Companies choose colors that they believe will motivate consumers to purchase their products and improve brand awareness. Colors have been used in color therapy to treat various diseases.

Color perception

Color psychology is a relatively new field that faces several challenges. The main difficulty that arises when studying this topic is determining how to measure the effect of colors. Color perception is very subjective because different people have different thoughts and responses to colors. There are several factors that affect the perception of colors, which makes it difficult to determine whether colors only affect our feelings and actions.

Factors affecting color perception include age, gender, and culture. In some cultures, for example, white is associated with happiness and purity. When a woman wears a white dress, is she happy because she is white or because she is married? One of the different cultures can wear white. Because, in these cultures, white is associated with sadness and death. These and similar factors should be taken into account when studying the influence of colors on human emotions and behavior.

Color associations

Although no direct causal relationship between color and behavior has been found, some generalizations about colors and their symbolic meanings have been identified. Colors including red, yellow, and orange are considered warm colors and encourage excited feelings.

Cool colors are at the blue end of the visible light spectrum and include blue, violet, and green. These colors are associated with calmness, coolness and calmness.

In graphic design and publishing, color symbols are often used to evoke certain emotions. Regardless of age, gender, culture, or not, research studies show that colors affect some people's physiology, behavior, and mood.

Red color

Thoughts, attitudes and feelings associated with the color red include:

- Caution
- Love
- Courage
- Aggression
- Rage

Red is the longest wavelength in the visible light spectrum. In Western cultures, red is associated with power, control, and power. It also indicates danger and creates a warning. At traffic lights, red lights signal to warn and stop signalers. Some animals, such as snakes, are red, meaning they are dangerous and deadly.

Red also indicates passion and invokes the fight or flight response. This instinct is triggered by the amygdala of the brain when we are faced with a dangerous or threatening situation. It causes us to fight or flee. The red substance raises the metabolism and blood pressure in the body, which should be ready for action in an anxious situation.

Blue

Scenic view of sea against clear blue sky

Associations with the color blue include:

- Confidence
- Efficiency
- Sweetness
- Security
- Grief

Blue is associated with calmness and serenity. It is a symbol of logic, communication and intelligence. This is due to low stress, low temperature and

low pulse rate. Blue is also associated with warmth, emotional distance and lack of indifference. Despite the negative associations, blue is often chosen as the most popular color in surveys conducted around the world.

In research, blue light has been found to reset our circadian rhythms, or sleep-wake cycles. The blue wavelength of light from the sun relieves the pineal gland from releasing melatonin during the day. Melatonin tells the body it's time to sleep. Blue light encourages us to stay awake.

Yellow

- Energy
- I hope so
- Be respectful
- Fear
- Weakness

Yellow is a bright color and the color most visible to the eye. It means happiness, friendliness and authority. Yellow is the color of optimism and creativity. It draws our attention and conveys caution, as yellow colors are often used on road signs, taxis and school buses. Interestingly, yellow is also associated with fear, cowardice and illness.

In green

Green represents ideas such as:

- Health care
- Thank you
- Favorites
- Ambitions
- Passivity

Green lies between yellow and blue in the visible light spectrum and represents balance. It is the color of spring and is usually associated with growth, life, fertility and nature. Green represents safety and is associated with prosperity, wealth, good fortune and finances. It is considered an imaginative, relaxing color for feelings of calmness and stress relief. Negative associations with living green include greed, jealousy, apathy, and insomnia.

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